

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 2.10 Practitioners’ Gaps and Requirements – 4th Publicly available annual report for industry and academia 2025

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Summary

This document contains the 3 publicly available reports developed from Work Package 2 practitioners' workshops. These reports outline the priorities of Law Enforcement at an operational level, and the opportunities for development across the three topics covered by the workshops:

1. Enhancing Digital Forensics Investigations with OSINT and Cyber Intelligence
2. Business Model of Ransomware, including Crime as a Service (CaaS)
3. IoT Environment for Digital Forensics Investigations

This report is intended to act as a steer for industry and academia.

1. Enhancing Digital Forensics Investigations with OSINT and Cyber Intelligence

The main goal of Digital Forensics (DF) is to uncover and analyse the collected data, produce actionable intelligence and evidence in support of investigations, and present findings for prosecutions. However, Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) face several challenges in all stages of the DF process. This is where Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) and Cyber Intelligence techniques and tools could be utilised to enhance DF and LEA investigations.

OSINT focuses on gathering and analysing publicly accessible information from a variety of data sources such as social media accounts, public government records, and internet search engines, to assess risks and threats, answer investigative questions and assist with attribution through the analysis of an individual's 'digital footprint'. This intelligence can support, for example, national security, law enforcement and business intelligence.

For LEA investigations this is a valuable capability across all types of crime. Open-source information will often be combined with restricted information held by law enforcement agencies, which can be used to collect evidence and intelligence relevant to an investigation.

Cyber Intelligence involves collecting information on cybercrime from a wide collection of public, private and open sources, and then processing and analysing that information.

The combined use of OSINT and Cyber Intelligence in a DF investigation can help to clarify objectives, optimise resource allocation, provide a clear picture of the risk(s), improve time management, and enhance decision making and evidence collection.

This practitioners workshop provided an opportunity and platform to discuss and evaluate how LEAs access and utilise OSINT to aid DF investigations. It explored the state of play from different participating LEAs, what problems investigators face regarding conducting OSINT

and Cyber investigations, and the needs of LEAs concerning technology, legislation, and standardisation.

1.1. Priorities of Law Enforcement in the field of Enhancing Digital Forensics Investigations with OSINT and Cyber Intelligence

LEAs face several challenges when conducting a DF investigation. These challenges include the volume, velocity, variety, veracity, and value of data. “Solutions which assist in the analysis and triage of this data” were therefore flagged as a priority of the group.

1.2. Opportunities for development within investigations involving Digital Forensics Investigations with OSINT and Cyber Intelligence

- Ability for LEAs to better aggregate data within their organisation – improved central storage of information from OSINT, cyber intelligence, and DF investigations to ensure all relevant data is available during an investigation.
- Tools required to improve management of aliases used or collected during the investigation process.
- Language and sentiment analysis - tools to accurately process and analyse non-English context or text and the emotional tone of content posted on social media platforms
- Improvement of engagement and cooperation processes for LEAs with Internet Service Providers (ISPs) and Social Media Platforms (SMPs).
- Improvement of cooperation and communication amongst LEAs - OSINT as investigations can often cross international borders, which poses jurisdictional difficulties.

2. Business Model of Ransomware including CaaS

Ransomware continues to be a persistent challenging area for Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs). It is connected to most, if not all, types of cybercrime activity and has become one of the most devastating types of attacks, impacting organisations of all sizes worldwide and individuals alike.

Ransomware has been one of the main threats over the last year, with numerous high-profile and highly publicised incidents. However, the ransomware threat landscape is changing, with the prevalence of multiple extortion techniques and the criminals' objectives going beyond solely financial gains, such as accessing Intellectual Property and other sensitive data, hacktivism, and professionalisation of the cybercrime market.

The malicious practice of targeting victims' multiple times has also become increasingly prevalent, where criminals may use previously identified weaknesses or make use of stolen

credentials to launch successive attacks on the same victim. Alongside this, criminals use of XaaS (as-a-service) remains popular due to the efficient and highly profitable business models.

At this CYCLOPES practitioners' workshop, we would like participants to consider and discuss how the LEA approaches and tactics for investigating ransomware cases can be changed and modified to be more coordinated, targeted and effective.

2.1. Priorities of Law Enforcement in conducting DF Investigations involving Ransomware including CaaS

LEAs face several challenges when conducting a DF investigation involving ransomware. These challenges include lack of cooperation from other countries, crypto-exchanges, ISPs and SMPs. "Solutions which assist in improved knowledge and data exchange" was therefore highlighted as a priority of the Group.

2.2. Opportunities for development within Investigations involving Ransomware including CaaS

- Collaborative platform for LEA-to-LEA information exchange
- AI tools for chat analysis
- Technologies for automatic/more efficient parsing of different entities and leads within cases
- Courses to train LEA practitioners to conduct online covert investigations
- Training for the judiciary
- More multi-disciplinary teams within policing
- Harmonising data retention periods between countries

3. IoT Environment in Digital Forensic Investigations

Building on previous workshops that looked at IoT devices individually and Cloud Services, this workshop shifted the focus to the relationships and interactions between IoT devices within their ecosystems and the opportunities and challenges for LEA and digital forensics investigations. The capability of IoT networks is growing at a rapid rate and transforming everyday life through smart home technologies, connected devices and wearables, offering numerous benefits such as enhancing convenience, energy management and health monitoring. These data rich environments present unique challenges for digital forensics due to the large volume and diverse formats of data produced. Investigations are further complicated by the different number of IoT devices that can now be located within a single crime scene, and the distributed nature of them, e.g. different operating systems, communication and data storage protocols.

Our aim in the workshop was to identify and share best practices within the CYCLOPES community, while highlighting gaps that must be addressed for LEAs to effectively investigate, manage and respond to challenges in the digital forensic examination of IoT ecosystems.

3.1. Priorities of Law Enforcement in conducting Digital Forensic Investigations in the IoT Environment

LEAs encounter numerous obstacles when carrying out digital forensic investigations involving the interactions between IoT devices. These challenges include the number of different types of IoT devices, the absence of scripts for these devices, encrypted devices and data not being stored in the device. “Sharing information on these device types and of best practices” was flagged as a priority of the group.

3.2. Opportunities for development within Investigations in the IoT Environment

- More knowledge sharing between LEAs
- A secure IoT data sharing platform, where information on IoT device data could be shared
- Enhanced IoT detection technologies and methodologies for use at crime scenes, including solutions that identify and catalogue IoT devices
- The development and adoption of data standards for IoT devices
- Comprehensive training programs for DF investigators which are specifically focused on IoT device forensics
- Review the current MLAT procedure to identify potential improvements that could enhance data acquisition when the data is hosted in another country

4. Conclusion

The 4th Annual Report for the CYCLOPES project highlights the progress made in WP2, which aims to unite Law Enforcement Practitioners and Digital Forensic Investigators to combat cybercrime. To date, 12 out of 15 Practitioner workshops have been successfully conducted, with participants from various European LEAs. These workshops focused on current trends and threats, helping to identify common capability gaps and requirements.

For the fifth year, WP2 will continue to select relevant workshop topics to address the evolving cyber landscape. The project aims to ensure the network of European LEAs remains active post-project, fostering ongoing collaboration and knowledge exchange. WP2 is on track to meet its objectives, committed to collaboration, delivering valuable data for industry and academia, and ensuring the project's legacy endures.